

General Sampling Method for the Variance Estimation of the Improved Deterministic Truncation of Monte Carlo Method Using the Dirichlet Distribution

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ABSTRACT

The Monte Carlo (MC) method provides highly accurate solutions of reactor problem by relying on minimal assumptions. However, it is often constrained by its significant computational expense. The Improved Deterministic Truncation of Monte Carlo (iDTMC) method was developed to address this limitation, accelerating the convergence of the fission source distribution and obtain pin-wise reactor solution by coupling MC simulations with a deterministic solution. Although the iDTMC solution is derived from a deterministic solver, the parameters used to construct the problem are inherently uncertain, thereby introducing uncertainty into the solution itself. To quantify this uncertainty, we propose a methodology wherein deterministic parameters are sampled to create a corresponding set of problems. The uncertainty observed in the solutions to these problems serves as an estimate of the real variance. A critical challenge in this approach is the preservation of strong node-wise and parameter-wise correlations, which is crucial for an accurate estimation. To this end, we introduce a implicit Correlated Sampling (iCS) method founded on the Dirichlet distribution, which implicitly maintains correlations during the generation of parameter sets. This approach enables a reliable estimation of variance in iDTMC solutions while circumventing the need for independent batch calculations, ultimately enhancing the reliability of the iDTMC method in practical reactor analysis.

Keywords: Monte Carlo method, iDTMC, real variance, correlations, Dirichlet distribution

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactor analysis is a critical aspect of nuclear reactor design, essential for ensuring both safety and economic viability. The core of this analysis involves solving the neutron transport equation to determine key parameters like the multiplication factor and flux distribution. Since a direct analytical solution to this equation is infeasible, the field has largely adopted two competing methodologies: deterministic methods, which are computationally efficient but rely on numerous approximations, and the Monte Carlo (MC) method, which is highly accurate due to its use of minimal assumptions.

In the MC method, the life of individual neutrons is simulated as they travel from a fission source distribution (FSD) until they are absorbed or escape the system, with quantities of interest being tallied throughout this process. For eigenvalue problems, however, the FSD is itself dependent on the unknown neutron flux. This dependency necessitates running preliminary inactive cycles to allow the FSD to converge before beginning the active cycles where the final solution is tallied. Consequently, MC simulations are not only computationally intensive but also inherently statistical, meaning their results always possess a degree of uncertainty.

To mitigate these challenges, the Improved Deterministic Truncation of Monte Carlo (iDTMC) method was developed. Implemented in KAIST's in-house MC code, iMC [1]. The iDTMC method is a hybrid

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approach that couples MC simulations with deterministic solutions to enhance computational efficiency. During the inactive cycles, coarse-mesh deterministic solutions are used to accelerate FSD convergence. Once converged, fine-mesh deterministic solutions are performed during the active cycles to obtain pin-wise reactor solutions. Previous work has confirmed that iDTMC significantly reduces computational time compared to conventional MC simulations and has been successfully extended to transient and depletion calculations [1-3].

Although the final iDTMC solution is obtained deterministically, it inherits uncertainty from the MC tallied parameters used to construct the deterministic problems. A viable strategy to quantify this uncertainty is to sample the parameters, generate multiple corresponding deterministic problems, and then estimate the real variance from the variance of their solutions. However, the success of this strategy hinges on a critical requirement. The sampled parameter sets must preserve the complex correlations and statistical distributions of the original MC tallies.

Previous attempts to address this have been only partially successful. For instance, the Correlated Sampling (CS) method preserved parameter-wise correlations between cross-sections but failed to capture node-wise correlations [1]. Other approaches, such as the history-based batch method and first-order autoregressive models, were used to reduce inter-cycle correlations but did not adequately address the node-wise and parameter-wise dependencies [4-5]. Consequently, a comprehensive framework capable of preserving both parameter-wise and node-wise correlations simultaneously has remained elusive.

In this paper, we address this gap by proposing a iCS method based on the Dirichlet distribution for estimating the variance of iDTMC solutions. This method is designed to implicitly preserve both parameter-wise and node-wise correlations when generating sampled parameter sets. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. First, we provide a theoretical overview of the iDTMC method. Next, we detail the proposed Dirichlet distribution-based variance estimation approach. Finally, we present numerical results for problems, including the SMR model, to validate our method.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. The Improved Deterministic Truncation of Monte Carlo method

The iDTMC method is a hybrid technique that couples MC simulations with deterministic solutions to improve efficiency. In an MC eigenvalue calculation, inactive cycles are first run to converge the FSD, after which active cycles are performed to accumulate tallies. The iDTMC method streamlines this workflow in two key ways. First, during the inactive cycles, it employs p-CMFD to accelerate FSD convergence. Second, during the active cycles, it uses partial current-based Fine Mesh Finite Difference (p-FMFD) to obtain the final pin-wise reactor solutions deterministically. By deterministically truncating the MC solution during active cycles, iDTMC achieves an additional reduction of statistical variance, resulting in improved overall computational efficiency compared to MC-CMFD methods. This approach reduces the required number of both inactive and active cycles, leading to a more efficient calculation of accurate, pin-wise results.

The FSD acceleration is achieved by solving the one-group neutron balance equation (NBE) on a coarse mesh, assembly-sized nodes, at each inactive cycle. This p-CMFD calculation uses parameters tallied from each inactive cycle of the MC simulation. All deterministic calculations in the iDTMC method are formulated using a single energy group. The NBE is given by:

$$\sum_n \frac{A}{V_n} \left(J_{n+\frac{1}{2}} - J_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \right) + \Sigma_{a,n}^{MC} \phi_n = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \nu \Sigma_{f,n}^{MC} \phi_n \quad (1)$$

In this equation, n is the node index, A is the surface area, V is the node volume, J is the net neutron current, and k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor. The one-group cross sections for absorption, Σ_a^{MC} , and fission multiplied by the number of neutrons per fission, $\nu \Sigma_f^{MC}$, are obtained from MC tallies. The net current J is defined using partial currents and correction factors for the consistency with the MC. The resulting p-CMFD flux solution is then used to update the MC fission source for the next inactive

cycle by updating the weight of the FSD according to the ratio of deterministic and MC fission probabilities.

Once the FSD has converged and the simulation moves to active cycles, the p-FMFD method is employed. It solves the same NBE as Equation (1) but on a fine mesh, corresponding to individual fuel pins, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Node configuration in p-FMFD (left) and p-CMFD (right).

The parameters for this calculation are accumulated from all active cycles, and the resulting p-FMFD solution provides the final deterministic, pin-wise reactor solutions. Figure 2 provides a complete schematic of the iDTMC workflow.

Figure 2. Schematic of the iDTMC method.

This process effectively uses deterministic calculations to accelerate the initial MC convergence but also to reduce the statistical variance of the final solution with deterministic p-FMFD solutions during active cycles. Although the iDTMC solution is obtained deterministically, the p-FMFD problem is constructed using parameters tallied from the MC simulation. These parameters are inherently statistical, and they introduce uncertainty into the final iDTMC solution.

2.2. Uncertainty estimation in the iDTMC method

Estimating the statistical uncertainty, or variance, of the iDTMC solution requires a different approach than that used in conventional MC simulations. In MC, real variance is typically estimated from independent batch calculations, as the simple apparent variance from active cycles is known to be underestimated due to inter-cycle correlations. Since the iDTMC method yields a deterministic result, this concept of cycle-based apparent variance is not applicable. Our strategy, therefore, is to quantify

the uncertainty by generating and solving a batch of deterministic p-FMFD problems within a single iDTMC calculation. This is achieved by sampling the input parameters for the p-FMFD solver, the pin-wise cross sections, partial current, and fluxes. The variance observed across the solutions of these sampled problems then serves as an estimator for the true variance of the iDTMC solution.

The critical challenge in this sampling process is to preserve the inherent correlations among the MC-tallied parameters. These dependencies are complex, existing both parameter-wise within a single node and node-wise between nodes. Ignoring these correlations can produce unphysical parameter sets and lead to unreliable variance estimates. Previous studies have attempted to address this with limited success. A method that can comprehensively maintain these correlations has thus been needed.

2.3. iCS method for the uncertainty estimation of the iDTMC method

Preserving the complex parameter-wise and node-wise correlations is essential for accurate variance estimation. Attempting to model these dependencies explicitly, for instance by constructing large correlation matrices for every fine mesh, is computationally prohibitive. We therefore propose an implicit approach. The core insight is that the full set of p-FMFD parameters, P_i , tallied from any single active cycle i , inherently contains all the correct, physically-consistent correlations. By using these complete parameter sets as fundamental building blocks, we can generate new, statistically-valid sets that implicitly preserve these critical dependencies.

Our proposed sampling algorithm consists of three main steps. Suppose N sets of p-FMFD parameters, $P = \{P_1, \dots, P_N\}$, have been accumulated from the active cycles, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Accumulation of p-FMFD parameter sets.

To generate a new sampled set, P' , first, a vector of N random weights, $\omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_N\} \sim Dir(1.0, \dots, 1.0)$ is sampled from a symmetric Dirichlet distribution [6]. The unity parameters yield weights uniformly distributed over the simplex, reflecting the statistical equivalence of parameters tallied from active cycles and providing numerical stability in the sampling process. Next, a preliminary sampled parameter set, P_s , is created by taking a weighted sum of the original accumulated sets:

$$P_s = \sum_{i=1}^N \omega_i P_i \quad (2)$$

This step combines the original data in a novel configuration while preserving the implicit correlations contained within each P_i . Finally, the preliminary set is transformed to match the mean, E , and variance, Var , of the original accumulated data population. This ensures the final sampled set, P' , is statistically consistent with the original simulation results:

$$P' = \frac{P_s - E[P_s]}{Var[P_s]} \times Var[P] + E[P] \quad (3)$$

By repeating this process, we can generate any number of new parameters sets that are statistically consistent with the original MC data and, maintain the complex underlying correlations without the need for explicit and costly matrix construction. Unlike the CS method, which requires correlation matrix construction and decomposition, the proposed iCS method only performs weight sampling and weighted summation, resulting in negligible additional computational overhead relative to the iDTMC simulation.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The SMR model was selected for numerical analysis [3]. Its detailed configuration is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Fuel assembly configurations of the SMR model (left), radial (middle), and axial layout (right).

Neutronic analysis was performed using the iDTMC method. Each calculation employed 1,500,000 histories per cycle, with 15 inactive and 115 active cycles. The final 100 active cycles were treated as p-FMFD cycles. The number of inactive cycles was determined based on the convergence of the Shannon entropy. Each assembly was modeled as a coarse mesh and each fuel pin was modeled as a fine mesh.

The variance estimation of the eigenvalue was performed, and the results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Eigenvalue standard deviation for 1 to 100 p-FMFD cycle is the SMR model.

To evaluate the performance of our proposed variance estimation method, we first established a real variance by conducting 90 independent iDTMC runs. For our estimation, the variance was calculated from 100 sampled p-FMFD parameter sets generated at each active cycle. The presented results are the mean estimates from 30 independent runs, with corresponding 99.7% confidence interval to show the statistical spread.

A direct comparison reveals that the previously used CS method significantly underestimates the real variance for the test problem [1]. In contrast, our proposed Dirichlet-based sampling method produces a slight overestimation, yielding a more conservative and reliable uncertainty quantification. The underestimation of the CS method appears to stem from two key limitations.

The first limitation is its scope; it only samples the three main cross-sections while ignoring the statistical variations in neutron fluxes and interface currents. To isolate this effect, we ran a modified version of our proposed method that was similarly restricted to sampling only the cross-sections. This restricted approach also resulted in underestimation of the variance compared to our full implementation, confirming that the exclusion of fluxes and currents is a major source of error.

The second, more fundamental limitation is the handling of correlations. Even when restricted to sampling only cross-sections, our iCS method produced overestimated variance estimate than the CS method. This is because our approach implicitly preserves both parameter-wise and crucial node-wise correlations, whereas CS only accounts for parameter-wise dependencies among the cross-sections. To quantitatively verify this superior handling of correlations, we performed a follow-up analysis of the parameter sets using Pearson correlation coefficients.

To quantitatively verify that our proposed sampling method implicitly preserves the underlying correlations, we performed a detailed analysis of the sampled parameters from an SMR model simulation. We calculated the Pearson correlation coefficients for parameters generated by our iCS method and the previous CS method, comparing both against a reference solution derived from the original MC data. The analysis was divided into two parts, node-wise and parameter-wise correlations.

First, we assessed the ability of each method to reproduce the node-wise correlations between adjacent spatial nodes. The mean correlation coefficients for all adjacent nodes along each spatial direction, \hat{i} , was calculated as defined in Equation (4).

$$\rho_{node} = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \rho_{i,i+1}^X \quad (4)$$

Here, N_i is the number of nodes in given direction, \hat{x} , \hat{y} , or \hat{z} , $\rho_{i,i+1}^X$ represents the Pearson correlation between two adjacent nodes, i and $i + 1$, for parameter sampled using method X . Table I presents a summary of these mean node-wise correlations, comparing the results from each sampling method.

Table I. Mean node-wise correlations for various parameters.

ρ_{node}	X	Reference	iCS	CS
Σ_t	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.2017	0.2076	-0.0004
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.2021	0.2080	0.0003
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0163	0.0171	-0.0004
Σ_a	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.1006	0.1040	0.0001
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.1005	0.1038	-0.0002
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0107	0.0111	-0.0004
$v\Sigma_f$	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.1040	0.1076	0.0002
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.1044	0.1075	-0.0004
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0120	0.0123	-0.0004
ϕ	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.3135	0.3227	
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.3138	0.3225	-
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0653	0.0684	
J^-	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.3006	0.3091	
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.3011	0.3093	-
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0029	0.0027	
J^+	$\hat{i} = \hat{x}$	0.3000	0.3080	
	$\hat{i} = \hat{y}$	0.3006	0.3084	-
	$\hat{i} = \hat{z}$	0.0028	0.0026	

The results clearly showed that our proposed iCS method successfully reproduces the reference correlations for all parameters, including cross-sections, fluxes, and currents. In contrast, the CS method failed completely, yielding correlation values near zero. This is because it does not account for spatial dependencies, and as a result, it cannot sample fluxes or interface currents.

To quantify this difference, we calculated the mean absolute error between the correlations from each method and the reference values as defined in Equation (5).

$$e_{node} = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} |\rho_{i,i+1}^{ref} - \rho_{i,i+1}^X| \quad (5)$$

Table II presents a summary of mean absolute error of node-wise correlations.

Table II. Mean absolute error of node-wise correlations for various parameters.

e_{node}	X	iCS	CS
Σ_t	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0784	0.2433
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0782	0.2429
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0720	0.1546
Σ_a	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0803	0.1936
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0804	0.1932
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0718	0.1545
$\nu\Sigma_f$	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0804	0.1941
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0801	0.1938
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0709	0.1530
ϕ	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0741	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0739	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0723	-
J^-	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0747	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0744	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0716	-
J^+	$\hat{t} = \hat{x}$	0.0747	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{y}$	0.0743	-
	$\hat{t} = \hat{z}$	0.0722	-

This analysis revealed that the error from the CS method was two to three times larger than that of our proposed method. The small errors associated with our method confirm that it effectively preserves the crucial node-wise correlations present in the original MC data.

Next, we evaluated the preservation of parameter-wise correlations, which describe the dependencies between different parameters within the same spatial node. We calculated the mean correlation for key parameter pairs across all nodes, as well as the corresponding mean error relative to the reference as defined in Equation (6).

$$\rho_{parameter} = \frac{1}{N_{mesh}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{mesh}} \rho_i(X_1, X_2), \quad e_{parameter} = \frac{1}{N_{mesh}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{mesh}} |\rho_i^{ref}(X_1, X_2) - \rho_i^X(X_1, X_2)| \quad (6)$$

Here, N_{mesh} is the total number of p-FMFD nodes, and $\rho_i^X(X_1, X_2)$ is the Pearson correlation between two parameters, X_1 and X_2 , at the node i for parameters sampled with method X . Table III presents a summary of mean correlation and absolute error of parameter-wise correlations.

Table III. Mean correlation and absolute error of parameter-wise correlations for various parameters.

	(X_1, X_2)	Reference	iCS	CS
$\rho_{parameter}$	(Σ_t, Σ_a)	0.4514	0.4640	0.4469
	$(\Sigma_t, \nu\Sigma_f)$	0.3379	0.3480	0.3346
	$(\Sigma_a, \nu\Sigma_f)$	0.7955	0.8193	0.7876
$e_{parameter}$	(Σ_t, Σ_a)	-	0.0662	0.0060
	$(\Sigma_t, \nu\Sigma_f)$	-	0.0732	0.0048
	$(\Sigma_a, \nu\Sigma_f)$	-	0.0357	0.0082

As expected, the CS method—which explicitly models these specific dependencies—produced smaller errors. However, our proposed iCS method also performed well. Its resulting correlation values were reasonably close to the reference, and the associated errors were negligible compared to the mean correlation values themselves. This demonstrates that our method, without any explicit modeling, successfully and implicitly preserves the essential parameter-wise correlations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have developed and validated a novel sampling method for quantifying the uncertainty in iDTMC solutions. The proposed method, based on the Dirichlet distribution, generates new parameter sets as weighted combinations of those accumulated during the active cycles of a single MC run. This approach implicitly preserves the complex node-wise and parameter-wise correlations inherent in the simulation data, thereby providing a reliable variance estimate without the need for computationally expensive independent batch calculations.

Our numerical results for the SMR problem demonstrated that the method accurately reproduces the reference real variance with only minor deviations. A detailed correlation analysis further verified that both spatial and parameter-level dependencies were successfully maintained. These findings establish our proposed method as a robust and scalable framework for iDTMC uncertainty quantification, offering superior generality and accuracy compared to previous techniques like the CS method.

The flexibility of this framework also suggests significant potential for extension to more complex problems. Future work will focus on conducting a sensitivity analysis with respect to the choice of the weight sampling distribution, applying the method to fast reactor problems, which exhibit particularly strong node-wise dependencies and developing enhanced techniques to further mitigate the impact of any residual cycle-wise correlations.

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